

THE CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF FORMING EDUCATION AND EDUCATION IN PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *In fact, modern pedagogical technologies increase the productivity of the educational process, form the independent thinking process of students, increase students' enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, form the skills and competencies of solid mastering of knowledge, free use of it in practice. In primary classes, where the child's thinking is being formed, the skill of the teacher, his ability to skillfully apply pedagogical technologies to the educational process, search for new methods and methods of education, and creative use of pedagogical experiences are very important.*

Keywords: *pedagogical innovation, professional method, thinking, theory, practice, technology, high spirituality, culture, tradition, primary education.*

Today, our Republic, as an independent state, aims to build a democratic society and become one of the most developed countries in the world. This, in turn, is determined by the development of the innovative activity of primary education teachers. Pedagogical innovation is a means of enriching and developing the theory and practice of education and training by introducing unknown changes in the professional-methodological training process of teachers who previously worked in educational institutions during the educational process. In fact, modern pedagogical technologies increase the productivity of the educational process, form the independent thinking process of students, increase enthusiasm and interest in knowledge in students, form the skills and abilities of solid assimilation of knowledge, free use of it in practice. In primary classes, where the child's thinking is being formed, it is very important for the teacher's skills, his skillful application of pedagogical technologies to the educational process, the search for new methods and methods of education, and the creative use of pedagogical experiences. That's why introducing pedagogical innovations into the educational process, using pedagogical technologies in education, using various innovative methods and methods, and constantly seeking to increase the effectiveness of education has become the need of today.

A modern teacher should have a deep knowledge of the history, high spirituality, culture, and traditions of our people and be a passionate propagator of it in the classroom and in the community of parents. At the same time, it is necessary to raise children based on our national values, to be fluent in speech, and to have full mastery of literary language style and norms of expression and image tools. Such qualities characteristic of the teaching profession are formed by pedagogical etiquette. Pedagogical etiquette is a high professional quality of a teacher. It is a virtue that helps the teacher to be stable, to be able to control his emotions, to determine and determine the means and standards of pedagogical influence on children. In the pedagogical process, the teacher is the subject of moral relations. As the main person of the pedagogical process, he interacts with students, colleagues, and parents. Pedagogical etiquette is one of the most important aspects of pedagogues. Pupils, colleagues, parents, team of pedagogues and representatives of public

organizations are objects of pedagogical interactions for the teacher. Contacts with them happen in the process of fulfilling the tasks of educating the young generation. This means that people participating in the process of dealing have benevolent and positive feelings towards each other, mutual evaluation and appreciation of each other's qualities. Dealing with students requires the pedagogue's ability to communicate with his students. The teacher's interaction with students is considered as a means of education management, and it also performs the function of unification and replacement. The transaction takes place within the framework of mutual relations. Behavior, which is a means of management, accompanies the activity of students, and finally, it follows the activity of behavior, which is a means of management. Communication is a means of communication between people. Language is the main tool of communication. That is why language is called a tool of communication. If a person's language is sweet and his behavior is civilized, he will gain respect among the people in a short time. Eloquence never brings prestige to a person. That is why our thinkers who lived in the past taught us to treat language and words with respect. It should be taken into account that the changes taking place in our society in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres depend on the educational system, which determines the intellectual potential of our country in the future and is considered the main condition for its development.

At the same time, the growth and quality development of intellectual potential not only affects the increase in educational efficiency, the improvement of the system in this field, but also significantly affects the growth of all areas of this social system. That is why today one of the strategic directions in education is determined as the main factor of the innovative activity of educational institutions.

Realizing the need to reform the educational system, in practice requires educational institutions to join innovative processes, to see the opportunity to create oneself in the existing innovative space and, most importantly, to absorb specific innovations. This situation is very relevant today, because this process (innovation process) is a condition for the survival of educational institutions (both directly and metaphorically), and a condition for social protection of the relations of future generations and the team of pedagogues. Life presents educational institutions with new, seemingly impossible tasks, that is, working on the old ones, developing specific innovations and putting them into practice.

It is possible to understand the older generation, which approaches all news with extreme caution, is brought up in the spirit of faith in past riches and experiences, likes stability, as well as pedagogues who do not want any changes. In this case, it is necessary to understand that "pursuing innovative processes" is an integral part of our life today. Whether we like it or not, the process of market and market relations is going on behind the walls of our educational institutions. This process is directly related to us, because the concept of competition between educational institutions, their competitiveness, quality of education, social orders, all these are entering our lives.

In the literature on pedagogy, 4 main laws of the innovation process are distinguished: - the law of chaotic disorder of the pedagogical innovation environment; - the law of final realization; - the law of molding (stereotyping); - the law of periodic repetition and return of pedagogical innovation. In the law of unbridled disorder, holistic ideas about pedagogical processes and events are broken, pedagogical consciousness is divided, pedagogical innovation is evaluated, and it widely spreads the importance and value of innovation. Finally, the law of

fulfillment is the vitality of innovation, which sooner or later, spontaneously or consciously, comes to pass. The law of modeling (stereotyping) consists in the fact that pedagogical innovation has a tendency to stereotype thinking and move to practical action. In this case, the pedagogical pattern (stereotype) is forced to lag behind and become an obstacle to the implementation of other innovations. The essence of the law of periodic repetition and return of pedagogical innovation is that innovation is renewed in new conditions. The main result of such education is not the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, but the ability for personal growth, empathic interactions and high social activity aimed at personal effectiveness. In order to realize the future of life, a person consciously re-establishes self-activity and uses the opportunities of the educational process for this. In particular, this process is the period of student age, the period of youth is an important stage for starting this process. The next lesson of this concept is related to the development of pedagogical subjectivity: the student passes through the position of "learner", "reader", "teacher". If a higher educational institution is considered "not a place and time of study, but a place for young men and women to grow up" (D.B. Elkonin), then the pedagogical process in this higher educational institution is being educated through its implementation. The subject of creative self-reconstruction of the pedagogical process, which activates the student's self-development, is an opportunity for both the student and the teacher. The activity of the teacher will also change: from imparting knowledge on the basis of pedagogical technology through the work of a "master", he will become a designer of his future professional activity together with students in the position of "consultant", who organizes joint activities in order to form pedagogical skills in students. Accordingly, it becomes urgent to implement integrative educational technologies. In this matter, it is necessary for the Institute of Educational Design to take the lead in today's urgent issue. In addition, the block of pedagogic and psychological sciences in the field of teaching each subject in higher education should be engaged in the implementation of rapid technological research. It is worth paying special attention to the organizational-structural model of pedagogical education implementation. These are: focusing on small-scale, multi-level and multi-level models.

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